

**Have IMI2 821520 -
ConcePTION**

ConcePTION

**WP3 – Determination of drug
transfer and infant drug
exposure during lactation:
generation of quantitative and
translatable data**

D3.8 Individual PBPK model for predicting exposure of infants to selected drugs

** PBPK = physiologically-based pharmacokinetic*

Lead contributor	Julia Macente, Nina Nauwelaerts, Martje Van Neste, Miao-Chan Huang, Karel Allegaert, Anne Smits, Isabelle Huys, Pieter Annaert (7 – KU Leuven)
Other contributors	Rodolfo Hernandez Bonan (20 – BioNotus) Justine Marine Badee (38 – Novartis Pharma AG)

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	18-12-2023	Summary of infant PBPK models developed for three drugs

Contents

Document History	1
Abstract	3
Glossary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Methods	5
2.1 Adult PBPK models	6
2.2 Infant PBPK models	6
2.2.1 Infant PBPK models in Simcyp	7
2.2.2 Infant PBPK models in PK-Sim	8
2.3 Predictive performance of adult and infant PBPK models	9
3. Results	10
3.1 Adults PBPK models	10
3.2 Infant PBPK models	10
4. Discussion	16
5. Conclusion	17
6. References	17

Abstract

Introduction: Several pathologies require pharmacotherapy during infancy and childhood. Generating information regarding use and safety during early life is relevant for the development and labelling of drugs used in this population. However, knowledge of the physiology and pharmacokinetics in this population is still limited since the maturational physiology and ontogeny need to be considered. A promising tool to predict drug concentrations in the infant population is physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation. Work Package 3 (WP3) of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine drug transfer into human milk, and subsequent exposure of infants.

Aim: The aim of this deliverable is to report the development and qualification of the infant PBPK models using Simcyp® and PK-Sim® software to predict the plasma concentration time profile of amoxicillin, levetiracetam and valproic acid.

Methods: The PBPK models were developed in Simcyp® V21 (Certara, L.P., Sheffield, UK) and in PK-Sim® V9.1 (Open Systems Pharmacology) for amoxicillin, levetiracetam and valproic acid. First, a PBPK model was developed for adult healthy volunteers and qualified against *in vivo* clinical data. In a second step, the qualified adult PBPK models were extrapolated to infants by accounting for the physiological changes, ontogeny functions and values regarding the age dependency of anthropometrics. Clinical data from literature were collected for infants aged from 3 months to 1 year old and used for model development and qualification purposes.

Results: The adult PBPK models developed in Simcyp® and PK-Sim® for the three model drugs adequately described the observed plasma concentration time profiles, as well the PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{max} and AUC) in adult healthy volunteers. The infant PBPK models in both software platforms showed a good prediction of the pharmacokinetic parameters and were able to adequately capture the plasma concentration-time profiles when compared to the clinical data.

Conclusion: The presented PBPK models adequately describe the plasma PK of amoxicillin, valproic acid and levetiracetam in adults and infants. Integration of the qualified infant models with the corresponding lactation PBPK models, as previously developed using both software platforms, will result in a comprehensive maternal-infant PBPK model, allowing the simulation of systemic exposure to maternal medication in breastfed infants *via* human milk.

Glossary

ASCM1	Synthetase medium chain family member 1
ADME	Absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion
AUC	Area under the curve
BCS	Biopharmaceutics classification system
BID	Twice a day administration
BSA	Body surface area
C _{max}	Maximum (or peak) concentration in plasma
CV%	Percentage of coefficient of variation
GFR	Glomerular filtration rate
GI	Gastrointestinal
GM	Geometric mean
Mech Kim	Mechanistic kidney model
MD	Multiple dose
M&S	Modelling and simulation
PBPK	Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic(s)
PO	Oral administration
SD	Single dose
TID	Three times a day
UGT	UDP-glucuronosyltransferase
VPC	Visual predictive check

1. Introduction

In April 2019, ConcePTION was launched. ConcePTION is a private public partnership that aims to generate information about the use of drugs during pregnancy and breastfeeding: “Building an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding: validated and regulatory endorsed workflows for fast, optimized evidence generation.” Work Package 3 (WP3) of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine drug transfer into human milk, and subsequent exposure of infants. While this platform relies on non-clinical methodologies (*i.e.*, *in vivo* animal, *in vitro*, and *in silico*), the predicted outcomes are of clinical relevance (*e.g.*, concentration time profiles of drug in maternal blood and milk).

Several pathologies require pharmacotherapy during infancy and childhood (*e.g.*, infections, epilepsy). However, knowledge of the physiology and pharmacokinetics in this population is still limited since the maturational physiology and ontogeny need to be considered. In addition, differences in maturational physiology (*e.g.* growth) have been described between exclusively breastfed infants compared to formula-fed infants [1]. Therefore, generating information regarding use and safety of drugs during early life is relevant for the development and labelling of drugs used in this population. A promising tool to predict drug concentrations in the infant population is the physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation (M&S). PBPK M&S enables pharmacokinetic predictions based on integration of population-specific data regarding physiology with drug-specific data. These models can be used for bottom-up predictions in the absence of any measured (*in vivo*) concentrations in the “target species”. Although there are some limitations to this approach for the pediatrics population, *e.g.* limited pediatric pharmacokinetic data, high interindividual variability in physiological parameters especially for infant and neonates. Despite these limitations, PBPK modelling remains a valuable tool for exploring pediatric pharmacokinetics and can help in optimizing drug dosing strategies and supporting drug development for pediatrics. In addition, it represents a promising tool to predict the exposure of drugs in breastfed infants to maternal medication. The aim of this deliverable is to report the development and qualification of the infant PBPK models using Simcyp® and PK-Sim® software to predict the plasma concentration time profiles of amoxicillin, levetiracetam and valproic acid in infants.

2. Methods

The purpose of this modelling and simulation project, was to develop infants PBPK models for three drugs, namely amoxicillin (AMX), levetiracetam (LEV) and valproic acid (VPA). The models were developed with two different PBPK modelling platforms: (i) the open-source platform Open Systems Pharmacology, which consists of PK-Sim® v9.1 and MoBi, and (ii) the Simcyp simulator version 21 (Simcyp 21.1, Certara Inc, Sheffield, UK). The present report provides the general M&S approaches (and underlying assumptions) as well as the platform-specific details. The *in vivo* clinical observed data in human for all drugs were obtained from selected literature sources and the data were extracted using WebPlotDigitizer®. The general workflow used to develop the infant PBPK models is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - General workflow that was used in the present project to develop and evaluate the infant PBPK models.

2.1 Adult PBPK models

For each drug a PBPK model was developed for an adult population, which could be an adult healthy volunteer or adult patient. Drug data (e.g., physicochemical properties) were combined with physiology-related parameters to simulate the pharmacokinetic profile of a drug in a healthy adult volunteer or patient. A first set of observed data in healthy volunteers (i.e., a training dataset) was used to build the model. If necessary, parameters were estimated to fit the observed data, implying the so-called middle-out approach. The predictive performance of the model was then evaluated with a second dataset (evaluation/verification dataset). Virtual populations were selected to closely match the enrolled individuals in the respective *in vivo* clinical trials, when available, with regards to dosing regimen, route of administration, gender ratio and age.

2.2 Infant PBPK models

PBPK models for AMX, LEV and VPA were developed to simulate the exposure of drugs in infants using the PK-Sim and Simcyp paediatric simulator, by incorporating anatomical and physiological changes with age as well as the ontogeny of clearance pathways of each drug. Clinical data from literature were collected for infants aged from 3 months to 1 year old for each drug. Virtual populations were selected to closely match the enrolled individuals in the respective *in vivo*

clinical trials, when available, with regards to dosing regimen, route of administration, gender ratio and age.

Information regarding the PK study design, as well as the individual weight and dosing regimen for each infant was often missing. However, when such information was missing, the models were developed based on the average dose reported for the infant population. The doses administered were often reported in “mg/kg”, and if specific weight information was not available, the parameter was assumed based on the typical weight for the specific age range mentioned in each study.

More information about the model development and qualification can be found in the drug-specific reports, which are available upon request.

2.2.1 Infant PBPK models in Simcyp

The Sim-Paediatric population was used to develop PBPK models for AMX, LEV and VPA in infants. The ontogeny profile for hepatic CYP2C9 and UGTs in the PBPK model of AMX, LEV and VPA is described by a sigmoidal relationship of age vs. enzyme abundance relative to adult levels, as shown in Equation 1 (described in Simcyp Version 21).

$$\text{Fraction of adult CYP enzyme levels} = F_{\text{birth}} + \frac{(F_{\text{max}} - F_{\text{birth}}) \cdot \text{Age}^n}{\text{Age}_{50}^n + \text{Age}^n} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Where, F_{birth} is the fraction of adult enzyme level at birth, F_{max} is the maximal fraction of adult enzyme level, Age_{50} is the age at 50% of the adult enzyme level and n is the Hill coefficient.

For hepatic UGT2B7, an exponential equation was used and is shown in Equation 2.

$$\text{Fraction} = C_0 + C_1 \cdot \exp^{C_2 \cdot (\text{Age} - C_3)} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Where, $C_0 = 0.113$, $C_1 = 0.0425$, $C_2 = 0$, and $C_3 = 0$; age cap of 21 (which assumes UGT2B7 is at adult levels at ages >20 years old).

AMX and LEV are both classified as a biopharmaceutics classification system (BCS) class I compounds (high permeability and solubility) and being primarily eliminated through renal excretion. The ontogeny of the renal function, specifically the glomerular filtration rate (GFR), was integrated based on the approach described by Johnson *et al.*, 2007 [2]. For AMX, the mechanistic kidney (Mech Kim) model integrated within the Simcyp simulator was utilized. The Mech Kim model was scaled to infants considering the changes in the anatomical and physiological parameters, as described by Salem *et al.*, 2022 [3]. AMX renal OAT3 clearance was extrapolated from adults to infants assuming the ontogeny described by Cheung *et al.*, 2019 [4], as implemented in the Simcyp simulator. In adults, LEV is mainly excreted in urine, with a reported renal clearance of 0.6 mL/min/kg [5], indicating excretion by GFR and subsequent partial tubular reabsorption. The renal clearance values for adults were scaled to the infants based on GFR (Equation 3) [6]

$$\text{GFR} = (-6.106 \times \text{BSA}^2) + (99.054 \times \text{BSA}) - 17.74 \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

Where BSA represents the body surface area.

VPA is also classified as a BCS class I compound (due to high solubility and permeability) and is mainly metabolized in the liver by glucuronidation *via* UGT1A6, UGT1A9 and UGT2B7 with minor contribution of UGT1A1, UGT1A3, UGT1A8, and UGT1A10 [7]. The adult model was extrapolated

to infants integrating the ontogeny within the Simcyp pediatric simulator V21 (table 1), for which the age-dependent ontogenies were established [8,9].

Table 1- Ontogeny parameters of hepatic CYP2C9 and UGT enzymes.

Parameter	UGT2B7	UGT1A1	UGT1A4	UGT1A6	UGT1A9	CYP2C9
F _{max}	0	1	1.028	1.025	1.012	0.98
F _{birth}	0	0	0.05	0.142	0.0541	0.17
Age ₅₀	0	0.183	1.042	0.411	0.07228	0.0157
n	1	1.105	1.36	0.97	5.771	0.53
Age-Cap	21	25	20	15	0.16	5

F_{birth} is the fraction of adult enzyme level at birth, F_{max} is the maximal fraction of adult enzyme level, Age₅₀ is the age at 50% of the adult enzyme level and n is the Hill coefficient.

2.2.2 Infant PBPK models in PK-Sim

Infant PBPK models were developed in PK-Sim v9.1 for AMX, LEV and VPA. Information on physiological parameters (*e.g.*, blood flows, organ volumes, hematocrit) in adults and infants are available in the PK-Sim® database. The ontogeny functions in the PK-Sim database were used to scale the PBPK models for adults to infant PBPK models. The abundance (including population variability) of plasma proteins and enzymes/transporters that are integrated into PK-Sim are described in the publicly available 'PK-Sim Ontogeny Database Version 7.3' (PK-Sim Ontogeny Database Version 7.3) [10]. The ontogeny of human serum albumin and enzymes/transporters was described as age-dependent activity which is relative to nonpregnant adult level using equation 4. For human serum albumin, the serum albumin concentration reported by McNamara et al [11] was used as a surrogate of activity.

$$A = \frac{PMA^n}{A_{0.5}^n + PMA^n} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

Where: PMA represents the post-menstrual age in weeks, A, the activity at PMA, A_{0.5}, the PMA at 50 % activity compared to adult, n, the Hill coefficient, and GeoSD, the geometric standard deviation. The fitted function in the PK-Sim Ontogeny database has the parameter estimations as the followings: n = 3.240 A0.5 = 21.533 GeoSD n = 1.284 GeoSD A0.5 = 1.205 GeoSD adult = 1.177

As mentioned in 2.2.1, renal excretion is the predominant elimination pathway for AMX. It is excreted for 60-80% unchanged in the urine via glomerular filtration and tubular secretion. A small fraction is metabolized to penicilloic acid, which was implemented in the PBPK model as total hepatic clearance.

For LEV, the renal elimination was implemented as kidney plasma clearance. LEV also undergoes some metabolism. The exact enzymes involved in the metabolism of levetiracetam are not known, but it is often assumed that esterases in blood and liver are involved. In the PBPK model, we assumed that CES1 is responsible for the metabolism and that CES1 is expressed only in liver and blood cells at the same level. The relative expression was manually put to 1 in liver and blood cells. Michaelis-Menten kinetics were implemented based on the data reported by Benedetti et al. 2003 [12]. The V_{max} was optimized in the adult PBPK model based on the fraction metabolized (34%) and the fraction excreted

in urine (66%). There is no ontogeny profile available for CES1 in PK-Sim.

For VPA, the glucuronidation via the different UGT enzymes was implemented as Michaelis-Menten kinetics based on *in vitro* data [13]. For the infant PBPK model, the expression of UGT1A1/3/4/6/8/9/10 were based on the default ontogeny profile for UGT1A1 in PK-Sim (table 2). The expression of UGT2B7 was based on the default ontogeny profile for UGT2B7 in PK-Sim table 2.

Table 2-Ontogeny parameters of hepatic CYP2C9 and UGT enzymes.

Parameter	UGT1A1	UGT2B7	CYP2C9
n	20.670	6.543	9.390
A _{0.5}	50.754	72.533	35.447
GeoSD n	1.066	1.023	1.055
GeoSD A _{0.5}	1.0844	1.554	1.592
GeoSD adult	1.367	1.595	1.793

A_{0.5}: post-menstrual age in weeks at 50% activity compared to adults; GeoSD: geometric standard deviation; GeoSD adult: geometric standard deviation in activity observed in adults; n: Hill coefficient.

About 40% of the metabolism of VPA occurs via mitochondrial β -oxidation. In the PBPK model, we assumed that acyl-coenzyme A synthetase medium chain family member 1 (ASCM1) was responsible for this pathway. Intrinsic clearance of ASCM1 was estimated in the adult PBPK model via parameter identification, based on the assumption that this pathway accounts for 40% of the metabolism. The ontogeny profile for ASCM1 is not available in PK-Sim.

Cytochrome P450 (CYP) oxidation is responsible for < 10% of the metabolism. In the PBPK model, we assumed that this was via CYP2C9. The intrinsic clearance was estimated via parameter identification in the adult PBPK model, based on the assumption that this pathway accounts for 10% of the metabolism. For the infant PBPK model, the expression of CYP2C9 was scaled based on the default ontogeny function available in PK-Sim (table 2). The ontogeny profile of CYP2C9 in the liver in PK-Sim is described based on previously published data [14]–[16]. A small fraction (< 3%) is excreted unchanged in the urine. The kidney plasma clearance was estimated via parameter identification in the adult PBPK model, based on the assumption that this pathway accounts for 1% of the metabolism.

2.3 Predictive performance of adult and infant PBPK models

The predictive performance of the PBPK models was evaluated comparing the simulated plasma concentration-time profiles against the available clinical observed data reported in literature for each drug. The PBPK model was accepted when the primary PK parameters (*i.e.*, the maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) and area under the curve (AUC)) were within 2-fold error margin, as outlined by the European Medicines Agency in 2018 and Food and Drug Administration in 2020 [17], [18].

3. Results

3.1 Adults PBPK models

The PBPK models developed for three drugs (amoxicillin, levetiracetam and valproic acid) were qualified against clinical data in adult healthy volunteers and/or patients using the PK-Sim and Simcyp software. The PBPK models were able to adequately capture the plasma concentration-time profiles as well as the primary PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{max} and AUC) in adult healthy volunteers and/or patients. Additional details about the adult models for each drug using Simcyp and PK-SIM can be found in the corresponding drug-specific reports. For the models developed using PK-SIM, the adult models can be found in the recent publication “Generic Workflow to Predict Medicine Concentrations in Human Milk Using Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Modelling—A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project” [19].

3.2 Infant PBPK models

For each of the three models, the adult PBPK models were extrapolated to the infant population as described in the methods section. The AUC and C_{max} ratios calculated for three drugs in the Simcyp simulator and PK-Sim software are listed in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The PBPK models adequately predicted the observed plasma concentration-time profiles of AMX, LEV and VPA, as shown in Figure 2. The PBPK models for the infant population showed that most of the observations were within the 5th to 95th percentile predicted concentrations. The simulated and observed AUC and C_{max} values of AMX, LEV, and VPA were between 2-fold margin (see Figure 2).

Table 3-Observed and simulated PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{max} and AUC) of AMX, LEV and VPA using Simcyp v21.

Study ID	Dose (mg/kg)	Route / Regimen	Age median (range) (years)	AUC _{obs} (µg/mL.h)	AUC _{pred} (µg/mL.h)	AUC Ratio	C _{max} _{obs} (µg/mL)	C _{max} _{pred} (µg/mL)	C _{max} Ratio	Reference
Amoxicillin										
Fonseca 2002	15	PO/SD	1 (0.41-4.3)	28.09	29.64	1.06	8.12	9.02	1.11	[20]
Fonseca 2002	15	PO/TID	1 (0.41-4.3)	26.94	30.78	1.14	7.02	9.29	1.32	[20]
Fonseca 2002	25	PO/SD	1.20 (0.25-4)	36.36	52.71	1.45	11.8	15.23	1.29	[20]
Fonseca 2002	25	PO/BID	1.20 (0.25-4)	31.85	51.40	1.61	9.6	15.32	1.64	[20]
Wu 2002	32.6	IV/SD	0.911±0.572	74.57	141.29	1.40	-	-	-	[21]
Valproic Acid										
Herngren 1990	33.7	PO/TID	0.5-1.8	659.53	911.12	1.38	92.67	126.0 ₃	1.35	[22]
Levetiracetam										
Glauser 2007	20	PO/SD	0.08-0.5	226.31	298.55	1.32	28.70	22.83	0.80	[23]
Glauser 2007	20	PO/SD	0.5-2	158.92	279.71	1.76	23.50	28.91	1.23	[23]
Glauser 2007	20	PO/SD	2-4	189.02	276.16	1.46	26.59	29.65	1.12	[23]

AUC: area under the curve; C_{max} : maximum (or peak) concentration in plasma; AUC ratio: simulated/observed ratio for area under the curve ; C_{max} ratio: simulated/observed ratio for maximum (or peak) concentration in plasma ; BID, twice a day administration; IV, intravenous administration; MD; multiple dose administration; PO: oral administration; SD, single dose administration; TID, three times a day administration.

Table 4- Ratio between the PK-SIM-predicted and observed AUC and C_{max} of amoxicillin, valproic acid and levetiracetam.

Study ID	Dose (mg/kg)	Route / Regimen	Age range (years)	AUC _{obs} (µg/mL.h)	AUC _{pred} (µg/mL.h)	Ratio	C _{max} _{obs} (µg/mL)	C _{max} _{pred} (µg/mL)	Ratio	Reference
Amoxicillin										
Fonseca 2002	15	PO/TID	1 (0.41-4.3)	24.13	26.85	1.11	8.13	10.40	1.28	[20]
Fonseca 2002	15	PO/TID	1 (0.41-4.3)	26.95	29.30	1.09	7.02	10.82	1.54	[20]
Fonseca 2002	25	PO/BID	1.20 (0.25-4)	32.98	21.41	0.65	11.79	10.94	0.93	[20]
Fonseca 2002	25	PO/BID	1.20 (0.25-4)	28.71	25.78	0.90	9.60	13.21	1.38	[20]
Wu 2002	32.6	PO/SD	0.911± 0.572	74.19	54.93	0.74	-	-	-	[21]
Valproic Acid										
Herngren 1990	33.7	PO/TID	0.5-1.8	659.53	796.55	1.21	92.67	107.23	1.16	[22]
Levetiracetam										
Glauser 2007	20	PO/SD	0.08-0.5	226.31	213.67	0.94	28.70	29.12	1.01	[23]
Glauser 2007	20	PO/SD	0.5-2	158.92	227.36	1.43	23.50	32.22	1.37	[23]
Glauser 2007	20	PO/SD	2-4	189.03	243.80	1.29	26.60	32.12	1.21	[23]

AUC: area under the curve; C_{max}: maximum (or peak) concentration in plasma; AUC ratio: simulated/observed ratio for area under the curve ; C_{max} ratio: simulated/observed ratio for maximum (or peak) concentration in plasma ; BID, twice a day administration; IV, intravenous administration; MD; multiple dose administration; PO: oral administration; SD, single dose administration; TID, three times a day administration.

Figure 2- Predictive performance of adult or infant PBPK models using PK-Sim (red) and Simcyp (blue) for C_{max} (A) and AUC_{0-t} (B) of amoxicillin, valproic acid and levetiracetam.

Figure 3-Simulated plasma concentration time profile of amoxicillin using Simcyp®. Black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles- Symbols represent mean observed data from Fonseca et al. (2002) after oral administration of 15mg/kg of amoxicillin in infants aged from 0.41 to 4.3 years old [20].

Figure 4-Simulated plasma concentration time profile of amoxicillin concentrations obtained in Simcyp, black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles. Symbols represent mean observed data obtained from Fonseca et al. (2002) after oral administration of 25mg/kg of amoxicillin in infants aged from 0.25 to 4 years old [20].

Figure 5-Simulated plasma concentration time profile of valproic acid concentrations using Simcyp, , black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles. Symbols represent observed data obtained from Hengren et al. (1990) after oral administration of 33.7mg/kg/day as t.i.d. regimen in infants aged from 0.5 to 1.8 years old children [22].

Figure 6- Simulated concentration time profile of levetiracetam concentrations using Simcyp. Black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles. Symbols represent observed data obtained from Glauser et al. (2006); triangles (1-6 months old); circles (6 months to 2 years old); square (2 to 4 years old) after oral administration of 20mg/kg[23].

Figure 7- Simulated plasma concentration time profile of amoxicillin using PK-SIM, black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles- Symbols represent mean observed data from Fonseca et al. (2002) after oral administration of 15mg/kg of amoxicillin in infants aged from 0.41 to 4.3 years old [2].

Figure 8- Simulated plasma concentration time profile of amoxicillin concentrations obtained in PK-SIM, black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles. Symbols represent mean observed data obtained from Fonseca et al. (2002) after oral administration of 25mg/kg in infants aged from 0.25 to 4 years old children [2].

Figure 9- Simulated plasma concentration time profile of valproic acid concentrations obtained in PK-SIM, black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles. Symbols represent observed data obtained from Hengren et al. (1990) after oral administration of 33.7mg/kg/day as t.i.d. regimen in infants aged from 0.5 to 1.8 years old [4].

Figure 10- Simulated d concentration time profile of levetiracetam concentrations using Simcyp, black dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentile profiles. Symbols represent observed data obtained from Glauser et al. (2006) ; triangles (1-6 months old); circles (6 months to 2 years old); square (2 to 4 years old) after oral administration of 20mg/kg [5].

4. Discussion

The objective of this deliverable was to report the development and qualification of the infants PBPK models using Simcyp and PK-SIM software to predict the plasma concentration time profile of amoxicillin, levetiracetam and valproic acid. The models were evaluated based on their ability to predict the plasma concentrations after oral or intravenous administration of the drugs to infants in the context of paediatric pharmacotherapy. Both Simcyp and PK-Sim demonstrated to adequately capture the plasma concentration-time profiles as well as the primary PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{max} and AUC) (*i.e.* < 2-fold bias) in adults. More information about the model development and qualification of predictive performance for adults can be found in the drug-specific reports, which are available upon request.

The qualified adult models were used to develop the plasma concentration profile in infants populations for each drug using a pediatric population within each software, *i.e.* by accounting for age-related different anatomical and physiology process, as well incorporating the ontogeny profiles. The infant PBPK models exhibited a good prediction accuracy (without estimation or fitting of parameters) when compared to observed clinical data reported in literature, with AUC and C_{max} ratio values ranging from 1.06 to 1.64 for Simcyp and 0.65 to 1.54 for PK-Sim, respectively [17], [18].

However, it is important to note the limitations encountered during the PBPK models development process. Specifically, the limited availability of clinical data in the pediatric population for model qualification purposes for the three proposed drugs, since, infants are rarely involved in clinical studies, due to ethical concerns [24]. One of the examples is for valproic acid, which is not recommended for pediatric use under 6 years old [25].

As part of an ongoing WP3 effort, these infant PBPK models will be optimized by integrating further information related to the specific physiological aspects of the exclusively breastfed infant. The collection of this physiological information is another objective of WP3 (Task 3.5). Furthermore,

differences in the maturational physiology of infants fed human milk or formula milk have been described regarding the growth, fat mass and lean mass of infants. For instance, breastfed infants take longer to recover their birth weight after initial weight loss in the first days of life [26]. A systematic search has been conducted in the literature to collect the maturational physiology of infants fed human milk. This data will be implemented in PBPK software as an exclusively breastfed infant population. PBPK models using this special population, will allow us to make more accurate predictions of drug exposure in exclusively breastfed infants and the drug transfer through human milk after maternal drug intake.

Sensitivity analyses will be performed to assess the impact of the changes in specific physiological parameters unique to breastfed infants (e.g., milk composition (e.g., fat content, protein content) and milk intake rate) on drug exposure in breastfed infants.

These analyses can lead to a better understanding of how variations in breastfeeding-related factors affect drug levels in infants.

These drugs were selected for further inclusion in maternal-infant PBPK models to assess the exposure of infants to maternal medication *via* human milk intake and will be described in the deliverable “D3.9-Integrated mother-infant PBPK model verified against human lactation data”. The integrated maternal-infant model will provide a better understanding of the drug transfer after maternal intake through human milk and consequently the infant drug exposure. The daily infant dose *via* breastfeeding will be used as a dosing regimen for the infant PBPK model, allowing to determine the relative infant exposure.

5. Conclusion

Overall, the developed infant PBPK models using two PBPK modelling software platforms (Simcyp® as industry standard and PK-Sim® as open source alternative) showed a good prediction of the plasma concentration-time profiles of amoxicillin, levetiracetam and valproic acid. Integration of the qualified infant models with the lactation PBPK models, as previously developed using both software platforms, will result in a comprehensive maternal-infant PBPK model, allowing the simulation of systemic exposure in breastfed infants *via* human milk.

6. References

- [1] E. R. J. Giugliani, “Growth in exclusively breastfed infants,” *Jornal de Pediatria*, vol. 95. Elsevier Editora Ltda, pp. 79–84, Mar. 01, 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.jpmed.2018.11.007.
- [2] T. N. Johnson, A. Rostami-Hodjegan, and G. T. Tucker, “Prediction of the Clearance of Eleven Drugs and Associated Variability in Neonates, Infants and Children Background Methods,” 2006.
- [3] F. Salem, B. G. Small, and T. N. Johnson, “Development and application of a pediatric mechanistic kidney model,” *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 854–866, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1002/psp4.12798.
- [4] K. W. K. Cheung *et al.*, “A Comprehensive Analysis of Ontogeny of Renal Drug Transporters: mRNA Analyses, Quantitative Proteomics, and Localization,” *Clin Pharmacol Ther*, vol. 106, no. 5, pp. 1083–1092, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1002/cpt.1516.
- [5] P. N. Patsalos, “Pharmacokinetic profile of levetiracetam toward ideal characteristics,” *Pharmacol Ther*, vol. 85, no. 2, pp. 77–85, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0163-7258(99)00052-2.
- [6] T. N. Johnson, A. Rostami-Hodjegan, and G. T. Tucker, “Prediction of the Clearance of Eleven Drugs and Associated Variability in Neonates, Infants and Children Background Methods,” 2006.

- [7] B. T. Ethell, G. D. Anderson, and B. Burchell, "The effect of valproic acid on drug and steroid glucuronidation by expressed human UDP-glucuronosyltransferases," *Biochem Pharmacol*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 1441–1449, May 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0006-2952(03)00076-5.
- [8] J. Badée *et al.*, "Characterization of the Ontogeny of Hepatic UDP-Glucuronosyltransferase Enzymes Based on Glucuronidation Activity Measured in Human Liver Microsomes," *J Clin Pharmacol*, vol. 59, no. S1, pp. S42–S55, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1002/jcph.1493.
- [9] S. N. Liu, J. B. L. Lu, C. J. W. Watson, P. Lazarus, Z. Desta, and B. T. Gufford, "Mechanistic assessment of extrahepatic contributions to glucuronidation of integrase strand transfer inhibitors," *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 535–544, May 2019, doi: 10.1124/dmd.118.085035.
- [10] "PK-Sim® Ontogeny Database."
- [11] P. J. Mcnamara and J. Alcorn, "Protein Binding Predictions in Infants," 2002. [Online]. Available: <http://www.aapspharmsci.org>
- [12] M. Strolin Benedetti, R. Whomsley, J. M. Nicolas, C. Young, and E. Baltes, "Pharmacokinetics and metabolism of ¹⁴C-levetiracetam, a new antiepileptic agent, in healthy volunteers," *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*, vol. 59, no. 8–9, pp. 621–630, 2003, doi: 10.1007/s00228-003-0655-6.
- [13] U. A. Argikar and R. P. Remmel, "Effect of aging on glucuronidation of valproic acid in human liver microsomes and the role of UDP-glucuronosyltransferase UGT1A4, UGT1A8, and UGT1A10," *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 229–236, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.1124/dmd.108.022426.
- [14] F. L??pplé *et al.*, "Differential expression and function of CYP2C isoforms in human intestine and liver," *Pharmacogenetics*, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 565–575, Sep. 2003, doi: 10.1097/00008571-200309000-00005.
- [15] S. B. Koukouritaki *et al.*, "Developmental Expression of Human Hepatic CYP2C9 and CYP2C19," *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, vol. 308, no. 3, pp. 965–974, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1124/jpet.103.060137.
- [16] M. W. Linder, R. A. Prough, and R. Valdes, "Pharmacogenetics: a laboratory tool for optimizing therapeutic efficiency.," *Clin Chem*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 254–66, Feb. 1997.
- [17] Green and Dionna, "Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Analyses — Format and Content Guidance for Industry," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fda.gov/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/default.htm>
- [18] E. Medicines Agency, "Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) Guideline on the reporting of physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation," 2018. [Online]. Available: www.ema.europa.eu/contact
- [19] N. Nauwelaerts *et al.*, "Generic Workflow to Predict Medicine Concentrations in Human Milk Using Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Modelling—A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 15, no. 5, p. 1469, May 2023, doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics15051469.
- [20] W. Fonseca, K. Hoppu, L. C. Rey, J. Amaral, and S. Qazi, "Comparing pharmacokinetics of amoxicillin given twice or three times per day to children older than 3 months with pneumonia," *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 997–1001, Mar. 2003, doi: 10.1128/AAC.47.3.997-1001.2003.
- [21] Y. E. Wu *et al.*, "Population Pharmacokinetics and Dosing Optimization of Amoxicillin in Chinese Infants," *J Clin Pharmacol*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 538–546, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1002/jcph.1752.
- [22] L. Herngren, B. Lundberg, and A. Nerg~irdh, "Pharmacokinetics of total and free valproic acid during monotherapy in infants," 1991.
- [23] T. A. Glauser *et al.*, "Pharmacokinetics of levetiracetam in infants and young children with epilepsy," *Epilepsia*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 1117–1122, 2007, doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1167.2007.01090.x.
- [24] S. Eyal, "Use of Therapeutics in Pregnancy and Lactation," *Pharmaceutical Research*, vol. 35, no. 5. Springer New York LLC, May 01, 2018. doi: 10.1007/s11095-018-2390-9.
- [25] K. Star, I. R. Edwards, and I. Choonara, "Valproic acid and fatalities in children: A review of individual case safety reports in VigiBase," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 9, no. 10. Public Library of Science, Oct. 10, 2014. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0108970.

- [26] P. D. Macdonald, S. R. M. Ross, L. Grant, and D. Young, “Neonatal weight loss in breast and formula fed infants,” *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed*, vol. 88, no. 6, 2003, doi: 10.1136/fn.88.6.f472.